

Preparation and Study of Hydroxytriazenes as Analytical Reagents. Part III. 3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-methyltriazene as a Reagent for Palladium and Copper

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3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-methyltriazene is found to be a highly selective reagent for the gravimetric determination of palladium and copper and for their separation from a large number of elements by direct weighing in the pH range from 1.0 to 6.0 and 3.2 to 6.0 respectively. The reagent offers a positive advantage over other hydroxytriazenes as it is fairly soluble in hot water and excess of it used during the precipitation of the complex can be easily washed. A comparative study of the reactions of 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-phenyltriazene and 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-methyltriazene has been made.

In Part II of this series (Gupta, Jain, and Sogani, this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 531) 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-phenyltriazene has been reported as a highly selective reagent for gravimetric determination of palladium and copper. In the present communication 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-methyltriazene has been described as an analytical reagent for the same purpose. This compound possesses identical chelating system to the compounds described earlier in Part I (Sogani and Bhattacharyya, *ibid.*, 1959, **36**, 563) and Part II (*loc. cit.*) with the difference that the oxime group is attached to a methyl group in place of a phenyl group. The characteristic complex forming properties are generally retained though precipitating property is lessened. This compound has a great advantage over other hydroxytriazenes in being fairly soluble in hot water and any excess of the reagent used during the precipitation can easily be removed by washing the complex with hot water.

A study of the reactions of the reagent with various ions shows that at low pH it reacts only with palladium, copper, vanadium, iron, molybdate, and vanadate. The complexes given by former two elements are stable towards heat in acidic medium. Selectivity can be increased by using proper masking agents and also by carrying out the determinations between pH 1.2 and 3.0 in case of palladium and 3.3 and 4.0 in case of copper.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagent was prepared by the method described earlier (Gupta and Sogani, this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 87). It was crystallised from 75% ethanol in the form of yellowish white needles, m.p. 110-11° (lit. m.p. 115-16°, Elkins and Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1346). (Found: N, 25.62. $C_8H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 25.45%). It is freely soluble in ethanol. Its solubility in water at 34° is 0.0308 g./100g. water and at 75° is 0.0905 g./100g. water.

Reactions with Various Elements.—The reactions were carried out by adopting the conventional procedures. Completeness of the precipitation was tested by applying the spot test on the filtrate. Details of the reactions of 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-phenyltriazene

and 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-methyltriazene towards various elements are recorded in Table I. The reactions of other phenylhydroxylamine derivatives are similar to the former and those of methylhydroxylamine derivatives are similar to the latter.

TABLE I

Comparative study of the reactions.

[Q=quantitative. N.Q.=Not quantitative. N.R.=No reaction.]

Elements.	3-Hydroxy-1- <i>p</i> -tolyl-3-phenyltriazene.	3-Hydroxy-1- <i>p</i> -tolyl-3-methyltriazene.
Fe ²⁺	pH 4.9 to 7.0, bluish black granular ppt., unstable towards heat; Q	N.R.
Fe ³⁺	Do	Below pH 2, blue colour; above pH 4, violet blue ppt.; N.Q.; masked by fluoride.
Cu ²⁺	pH 2.0 to 7.0, chocolate-brown granular ppt. stable towards heat; Q.	pH 3.2 to 7.0, reddish brown granular ppt. stable towards heat; Q.
Ni ²⁺	pH 4.4 to 7.0, bright yellow granular ppt. stable towards heat; Q.	Above pH 6.5, yellowish brown ppt. N. Q.; below pH 5, N. R.
Pd ²⁺	pH 1.6 to 7.0, yellowish brown granular ppt. stable towards heat; Q.	pH 1.0 to 6.0, violet brown granular ppt. stable towards heat; Q.
Mn ²⁺	Above pH 5.5, dirty brown ppt. unstable towards heat; N. Q.	N.R.
Cd ²⁺	Above pH 6.0, light yellow fine ppt.; N.Q.	N.R.
Ti ⁴⁺	pH 2.0 to 3.5, orange ppt. unstable towards heat; Q.	N.R.
Ce ⁴⁺	N.R.	Below pH 2, light yellow colour.
V ⁴⁺	Below pH 2.5, grassy green ppt. unstable towards heat.	Below pH 2, brown ppt. unstable towards heat; masked by fluoride.
Vanadate	Below pH 2.5, dark green ppt. unstable towards heat.	Below pH 2.5, unstable green solution; becomes turbid on keeping
Molybdate	Below pH 3.0, deep orange ppt. unstable towards heat	Below pH 2.0, yellow ppt.; becomes brown on keeping; N.Q; masked by fluoride.
Ag ⁺ , Au ³⁺	Reduced to metallic state.	Reduced to metallic state.

The phenylhydroxylamine derivatives develop an intense yellow colour in alkaline medium and hydrolyse on heating in weakly acidic medium. The hydrolysed products give blue colour in alkaline medium (Part I, *loc. cit.*) The methylhydroxylamine derivatives do not give such reactions.

1% Reagent solution (w/v) in 50% ethanol was used. Other solutions and instruments etc. were the same as described in Part II (*loc. cit.*).

Conditions for Quantitative Precipitation.—Determinations, made by using varying amounts of the reagent and under different pH conditions, show that palladium is completely precipitated between pH 1.0 and 6.0 by using double the required quantity of

the reagent and copper between pH 3.2 and 6.0 by using more than 2½ times the required quantity of the reagent. To increase the selectivity of the reagent, pH between 1.2 and 3.0 and between 3.3 and 4.0 were used for palladium and copper respectively.

As³⁺, Sb³⁺, Bi³⁺, Al³⁺, Cr³⁺, Be²⁺, Th⁴⁺, U⁴⁺, UO₂²⁺, Zr⁴⁺, tungstate, phosphate, borate, fluoride, alkali, and alkaline earth metals give no reaction with either of the reagents.

Properties of the Complexes.—Palladium complex is violet brown in colour and granular in nature. It is insoluble in ethanol, methanol, and ether and is fairly soluble in chloroform and benzene. It was crystallised from benzene in the form of fine crystals, m.p. 239°. It does not show any sign of decomposition before melting and can safely be heated to 120-30° to a constant weight in about half an hour. [Found: N, 9.82. (C₈H₁₀ON₃)₂Pd requires N, 9.63%].

Copper complex is reddish brown in colour. It is slightly soluble in ethanol, fairly soluble in acetone and ether, and freely soluble in chloroform and benzene. It is completely insoluble in 20% ethanol which can be used for washing the precipitate. It was crystallised from ethanol as reddish brown, shining crystals, m.p. 186°. It does not decompose before melting and can be dried to a constant weight between 110° and 120° in about half an hour. [Found: N, 10.56. (C₈H₁₀ON₃)₂Cu requires N, 10.72%]. The chelate can be represented as

(where M = Pd or Cu).

Procedure for Palladium.—Standard palladium solution containing 5 to 30 mg. of the metal was taken in a 400 c.c. beaker and to this were added 10% HCl (v/v; 5 c.c.) and 10% sodium acetate solution (w/v; 3 to 4 c.c.) so that pH of the solution after dilution was about 1.5 (pH can also be adjusted by using mineral acid alone). The solution was diluted to about 200 c.c. and heated over a water bath. To the hot solution, which may also contain varying amounts of foreign ions, an excess of 1% w/v reagent solution was added with constant stirring. For every mg. of palladium precipitated, 1 c.c. of 1% reagent solution was used. The palladium complex separates out as a violet-brown precipitate. The suspension was heated for about 40 minutes over a water bath during which period the complex became granular and the solution clear. The complex was then filtered hot through a sintered glass crucible No. 3 and washed with hot water 3 to 4 times till the filtrate gave no bluish violet colour with ferric chloride solution. It was then dried to a constant weight at 110-20° for about half an hour and weighed. The weight of the complex multiplied by 0.2454 gave the weight of palladium. The results are recorded in Table II.

Fe²⁺ does not react with the reagent, but during the course of precipitation some of it is invariably oxidised to the ferric state and gives blue colour with a slight turbidity. Zirconium salts are hydrolysed. The interference due to these and also due to vanadium and molybdate was eliminated by using fluoride (10 c.c. of 5% sodium fluoride solution). The interference due to hydrolysis of bismuth and antimony was avoided by using sodium potassium tartrate. Hydrolysis of cerium was checked by adding small amounts of solid ammonium sulphate.

Separation of Palladium from Platinum.—Qualitative reactions of the reagent indicate that it gives no reaction with platinum. But on heating on a water bath, platinum chloride was partially reduced to the metal by the reagent and higher results were obtained. The procedure was therefore slightly modified. To the solution of palladium containing platinum, after the adjustment of *pH* and dilution etc., the reagent solution was added in cold with constant stirring and filtered after about an hour. After two initial washings with cold water to remove any platinum left, it was washed with hot water to remove the excess of the reagent. It was then processed as usual. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Pd taken.	Foreign ion.	Pd complex.	Pd found.	Error.
6 mg.	-	0.0242 g.	5.94 mg.	-0.06 mg.
18	-	0.0735	18.03	+0.03
24	-	0.0978	24.00	±0.00
18	Ni ²⁺ , 0.1 g.	0.0733	17.99	-0.01
18	Co ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0735	18.03	+0.03
18	Zn ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0732	17.96	-0.04
18	Cd ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0733	17.99	-0.01
18	Mn ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0736	18.06	+0.06
18	Fe ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0734	18.01	+0.01
18	Fe ³⁺ , 0.1	0.0736	18.06	+0.06
18	Zr ⁴⁺ , 0.1	0.0734	18.01	+0.01
18	V ⁴⁺ , 0.1	0.0732	17.96	-0.04
18	Bi ³⁺ , 0.1	0.0735	18.03	+0.03
18	Sb ³⁺ , 0.1	0.0736	18.06	+0.06
18	Ce ⁴⁺ , 0.1	0.0733	17.99	-0.01
18	Cr ³⁺ , 0.1	0.0736	18.06	+0.06
18	Be ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0734	18.01	+0.01
18	Th ⁴⁺ , 0.1	0.0735	18.03	+0.03
18	Hg ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0737	18.08	+0.08
18	As ³⁺ , 0.1	0.0736	18.06	+0.06
18	UO ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0735	18.03	+0.03
18	Molybdate, 0.1	0.0733	17.99	-0.01
18	Tungstate, 0.1	0.0733	17.99	-0.01
12	Pt ⁴⁺ , 0.05	0.0490	12.02	+0.02
12	Pt ⁴⁺ , 0.1	0.0492	12.07	+0.07
12	Pt ⁴⁺ , 0.15	0.0491	12.05	+0.05

Procedure for Copper.—Standard copper sulphate solution containing 10 to 30 mg. of copper was taken in a 100 c.c. beaker and after adjusting the *pH* to about 3.40, 1% reagent solution (0.7 c.c.) was added for every mg. of copper present. When sodium potassium tartrate is used as a buffering agent, amount of the reagent is 1.5 c.c. of 1% solution for every mg. of copper. Rest of the procedure is the same as described in the case of palladium. The weight of the complex multiplied by 0.1623 furnishes the weight of copper. The results are recorded in Table III.

DISCUSSION

3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-methyltriazene has a distinct advantage over 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene (Sogani and Bhattacharyya, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, 28, 81, 1616) and 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-phenyltriazene (*loc. cit.*) which have been claimed to be superior

to the conventional reagents employed for the gravimetric determination of palladium as it is fairly soluble in hot water and excess of it used during precipitation can easily be removed by washing with hot water. Moreover, it affords a simple method for the separation of palladium from platinum. The reagent is not however, specific for copper as the working pH is slightly higher at which other elements interfere.

TABLE III

Cu taken.	Foreign ion.	Cu complex.	Cu found.	Error.
10 mg	-	0.9618 g.	10.03 mg.	+0.03 mg.
20	-	0.1232	19.99	-0.01
30	-	0.1853	30.07	+0.07
10	Co ²⁺ , 0.1 g.	0.0610	10.05	+0.05
10	Ni ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0615	9.97	-0.03
10	Zn ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0618	10.03	+0.03
10	Mn ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0620	10.07	+0.07
10	Cd ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0615	9.97	-0.03
10	Hg ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0619	10.05	+0.05
10	Fe ²⁺ , 0.1	0.0615	9.97	-0.03
10	Fe ³⁺ , 0.1	0.0618	10.03	+0.03
10	Cr ³⁺ , 0.1	0.0618	10.03	+0.03
10	Al ³⁺ , 0.1	0.0620	10.07	+0.07
10	Bi ³⁺ , 0.1	0.0619	10.05	+0.05
10	Sb ³⁺ , 0.1	0.0620	10.07	+0.07
10	Molybdate 0.1	0.0617	10.01	+0.01

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